

Genetic variability and correlation studies on grain yield and nutritional traits in F₂ population of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted to assess the variability and association studies of single plant yield and grain nutritional traits in F₂ generation of ADT 56 x *Kalanamak*. The experimental material consists of 222 F₂ plants along with the parents which were planted at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu. Data recorded on 14 yield and 3 nutritional related traits. This study revealed that, significant variability was present among the population for all the traits examined. High phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation coupled with high heritability and high genetic advance as a percent of the mean were recorded for the number of tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, panicle weight and thousand grains per panicle. The grain iron content with zinc content and also single plant yield per plant exhibited high positive and significant association with number of tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle and thousand grain per panicle making these traits effective targets for selection to transfer desirable characteristics to the next generation.

Key words : Grain iron and zinc content, yield traits, variability, correlation, F₂ mapping population, rice

Introduction:

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) stands as the predominant staple food and is the primary source of nourishment for almost 70% of the people. It is the crucial for the dietary and food security source of many Asian countries (Kumar et al, 2020). India is the world's second largest producer of rice, accounting for 22% of global production. Although rice output and productivity have significantly improved. The green revolution has led to plateaus in yield levels, limiting production efforts to satisfy the demands of a growing population, particularly in developing and underdeveloped countries. According to reports,

India's food security may be threatened by the country's projected population growth by 2050 (Fathima *et al.*, 2021).

Consequently, ensuring food security in the future is a very difficult issue, especially for Indian rice producers, since rice is essential to the nation's food and nutritional security. In order to break through yield barriers, rice varieties with high productivity levels and appropriate agronomic traits are needed. Hybridization has been identified as a key plant breeding strategy for achieving necessary diversity and high productivity levels. Additionally, selection in segregating generations must be directed toward producing superior yielding plants, for which yield variability and related qualities are crucial, and the development of efficient selection criteria for yield enhancement is necessary (Butardo *et al.*, 2019).

In such contexts, establishing sustainable breeding programs requires precise understanding of genetic divergence in yield components. Effective varietal improvement hinges on selecting parents with significant genetic differences for hybridization. Improvement for specific traits has been successfully achieved through the strategic use of F₂ segregating populations, facilitating the fixation of desirable combinations.

This study aims to assess variability, heritability, and genetic advance as a percentage of mean for grain yield and its components. Additionally, it explores the frequency distribution patterns based on skewness and kurtosis in the F₂ segregating generation for three selected crosses. Such analyses are pivotal for identifying superior genotypes with potential for higher yield and better performance under varying environmental conditions.

Materials and Methods :

The current investigation was carried out in the experimental field of Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu. Based on documented results, parents having contracting grain iron and zinc were chosen and crossed and developed mapping populations during 2023. The F₂ generation resulting from the cross between ADT 56 x *Kalanamak* were grown. Twenty six days old seedlings were transplanted in to the main field with a spacing of 30 cm x 30 cm in randomized block design. A total of 222 possible F₂ segregants of each plants were identified and labeled for further assessment. The recommended agronomic practices and crop protection measures were followed during the crop growth period. Each F₂ plant was harvested separately. Observations were recorded from randomly selected plants of each of the cross combinations and each of the randomly selected individual plant was tagged before anthesis. Data on all the seventeen characters namely DM-Days to Maturity, PH- Plant Height, NPT-number of productive tillers per plant, FL-Flag leaf length, FW-Flag leaf width, KL- kernel length; KB- kernel breadth; LBR-length-to-breadth ratio, PL- Panicle Length, PW-Panicle Weight, NB-Number of branches per panicle, FG-Filled Grains, UFG-Unfilled Grains, TNP-Total number of Grains per Panicle, TSW - Thousand Seed Weight, SPY - Single Plant Yield, FEB- Fe content in brown rice and ZNB-ZN content in brown rice and PCB- Protein content in brown rice were analyzed at TRRI, quality lab, with ED-XRF. The

recorded data was subjected to statistical analysis as analysis of variance, genetic variability and correlation analysis using R studio software.

Results and Discussion :

Mean Performance of F₂ generation: The results of genetic variability and other genetic parameters are shown and represented in Table 2 and Fig. 1. A perusal of the results on mean performance and range of the yield contributing and nutritional traits were studied in the present investigation revealed maximum range for single plant yield followed by grain iron, zinc and protein content while minimum range was observed for flag leaf width. Single plant yield for ADT 56 x *Kalanamak* ranges from 9.20 gm to 53.40 gm with mean of 27.26 gm, Similarly, filled grains and total number of grains were recorded in the study ranged from 73.50 to 284.10 with an average mea of 177.28. The maximum grain iron content noted as 16.90 kg/mg with a average mean of 12.32 kg/mg. Likewise, the maximum and minimum grain zinc content recorded as 36.75 and 17.47 respectively. The average value for the grain protein content was 12.83 %. Similar results were reported by Bharath et al. 2018, Singh *et al* 2020 and Swapnil et al 2020.

The phenotypic variation of ADT 56 x *Kalanamak* for Days to maturity ranged from 102.75 to 159.38 with a mean of 133.80. The average performance of Plant height noted as a 128.81 m (ADT 56 x *Kalanamak*) The number productive tillers per plant had an average mean of 20.48. Furthermore, the Flag leaf length and Flag leaf width recorded with mean of 39.22, 1.54 for ADT 56 x *Kalanamak*. Panicle length in the F₂ population ranged from 21.40 to 37.30 with a mean of 29.37. Whereas the panicle weight had an average mean of 2.85gm. Similarly, the unfilled grins and thousand grains per panicle recorded the average 65.03 and 245.31 respectively. The lowest mean was recorded in flag leaf width 0.70 cm. The results are in agreement with Singh et al. 2024. The current study discovered adequate genetic variation for all of the variables under investigation in the F₂ populations, and the materials could potentially be utilized for association mapping and as donors in Direct seeded Rice (DSR) conditions.

Variability studies

Estimating genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation is crucial for understanding the impact of environmental factors on various traits. Environmental influence on a character is measured by the difference in coefficients of variation between genotype and phenotype (Akinwale et al., 2011). Genetic parameters were categorized as follows: GCV and PCV into low (0-10%), moderate (10-20%) and high (>20%); Heritability into low (0-30%), moderate (30-60%) and high (>60%); and genetic advance as a percentage of the mea into low (0-10%), moderate (10-20%) and high (>20).

Table 2 displays the PCV and GCV values for characteristics of ADT 56 x *Kalanamak*. The study on variability demonstrated in this cross showed phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation were moderate for PH, FW, KB, L/B, FEB, ZNB and PCB. The high phenotypic and genotypic coefficients were recorded for NPT, FL, PW, FG, UFG, TGP and SPY. The phenotypic coefficient

variation (PCV) and genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) was highest for the UFG with 47.43 followed by SPY with 30.79 and lowest for KL 8.05 and 7.86 respectively. Furthermore, the minimal difference between GCV and PCV for all traits indicated that environmental factors had a negligible effect on the expression of these characteristics. The observations are in agreement with the inferences of Harisha et al. 2024. Both high heritability and high genetic advance were exhibited high by almost all traits except KL, which had moderate genetic advance mean. The cross combination had highest GAM value with 65.89 for NPT followed by UFG (57.45), SPY (55.63), PW (54.54) and FG (53.47).

Traits showing high PCV, GCV, heritability and genetic advance per mean suggests that these traits are influenced significantly by additive gene action. Selective breeding efforts targeting these traits could yield beneficial improvements. Similar finding were reported by Bharath et al. 2018, Abhilash *et al.* 2018, Khandappagol, et al 2019, Swapnil et al. 2020, Manojkumar (2023), Piyari (2023) and Niharika *et al.* 2024. Comparable results were observed by Prasanth et al. 2024 and Singh et al . 2020 who noted high heritability paired with substantial genetic advance for traits such as the number of productive tillers and filled grains per panicle. Heritability estimates of a trait reflects the reliability of predicting its phenotypic value. High heritability increases the effectiveness of selecting specific traits, thereby making their improvement particularly beneficial.

Correlation Coefficient studies

To determine the degree of association between the traits, a correlation analysis was done. Grain yield is a complex trait which is influenced by the interaction of a number of contributing characters. The estimated of the inter relationship between grain yield and other attributes like nutritional traits and among the yield traits would facilitate effective selection schemes to improve the yield. The graphical representation of these correlations is presented in Fig 1. In the cross combination (ADT 56 x *Kalanamak*) the trait grain Zn content had positive and significant correlation with Fe content (0.88). Therefore, the trait could be considered as important nutritional traits in all three cross combinations and selection for this trait would ultimately improvement of both traits from biofortification aspects. Dharwal (2017), Shivani et al (2018), Singh (2020), Swapnil (2020) and Perween (2022).

Furthermore, single plant yield had significant and high positive association with number of productive tillers per plant (0.51), Filled grains per panicle (0.58) and thousand grain per panicle (0.51) and panicle weight (0.24). Likewise thousand grain per panicle noted significant and positive correlation with filled grains (0.84), number of tillers per plant (0.65) and unfilled grains per panicle (0.54). The filled grains had a positive and significant association with number of tillers per plant (0.7) and panicle weight (0.28). Kernal length recorded significant and positive association with kernel breadth and LB ratio. Hence, this trait could be considered as important yield contributing traits in all the three combinations. Patel (2018), Priyanka (2029), Swapnil (2020), Piyari (2023), Perween (2022), Niharika (2024), Prashanth (2024) and Riyanto (2024). The trait of grain yield is not independent but is influenced by a complex network of associations with other that collectively impact the overall yield (Niharika et al. 2024). This indicates that these traits are major determinants of yield in rice. The

significant and high positive associations between yield and nutritional traits could result in positive and indirect selection, thereby enhancing nutritional and grain yield improvement. The trait yield and nutritional characters are not independent but influenced by a complex network of associations with other traits that collectively impact the overall yield and nutrient content. This indicates that these traits are major determinants of yield and nutritional traits in rice. The significant and positive correlations between yield and its components and nutritional traits suggest that selecting for these traits could result in positive indirect selection, there by enhancing grain yield and grain nutrient content improvement. The study identified the following lines as promising based on their yield and nutritional traits: KD 11-152, KD 11-176 and KD 11- 205.

Conclusion

The current study concluded that grain iron content with zinc content and also single plant yield per plant and number of tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle and thousand grain per panicle exhibited high coefficients of variation, making these traits effective targets for selection to transfer desirable characteristics to the next generation. High phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation coupled with high heritability and high genetic advance as a percent of the mean were recorded for the number of tillers per plant, filled grains per panicle, panicle weight and thousand grains per panicle. These findings indicate that direct selection is highly effective for these traits.

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Authors' contributions

All authors listed have made a substantial, direct, and intellectual contribution to the work, and approved it for publication.

Table 1. Parents used in the study

Parents	Parentage	Characters	Source
ADT 56	WGL1437/ MDU5	Short duration, good cooking & eating qualities. Moderately resistant to leaf blast, grain discoloration, stem borer and leaf folder	TRRI, Aduthurai
<i>Kalanamak</i>	Landrace	Short duration, Finest quality, resistant to blast. Cooked rice is fluffy, soft, non-sticky, sweet, and easily digestible with relatively longer shelf-life. It had 15.6 mg kg-1 of iron. It is famous for taste, palatability, and aroma	TRRI, Aduthurai

Table 2. Estimation of variability studies in ADT56×*Kalanamak* F₂ population

Parameters	Cross	DM	PH	NPT	FL	FW	KL	KB	L/B
Mean	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	133.80	128.81	20.48	39.22	1.54	6.57	2.26	2.98
Maximum	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	159.38	165.58	38.82	67.23	2.50	8.50	2.90	4.83
Minimum	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	102.75	90.78	6.83	25.42	0.70	5.40	1.20	2.07
PCV	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	10.28	11.85	32.04	21.22	19.52	8.05	13.29	15.40
GCV	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	10.18	11.73	32.01	20.84	19.51	7.86	13.26	15.36
H ₂	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	98.05	97.96	99.82	96.38	99.97	95.39	99.42	99.45
GAM	<i>ADT56×Kalanamak</i>	20.76	23.91	65.89	42.14	40.19	15.82	27.23	31.55

Parameters	Crosses	PL	PW	FG	UFG	TGP	SPY	FEB	ZNB	PCB
Mean	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	29.37	2.85	177.28	65.03	242.31	27.26	12.32	25.03	8.80
Maximum	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	37.30	5.30	284.10	193.30	469.60	53.40	16.90	36.75	11.54
Minimum	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	21.40	1.44	73.50	7.80	101.80	9.20	8.60	17.47	7.21
PCV	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	11.32	26.62	26.98	47.43	23.37	30.79	12.36	12.88	10.15
GCV	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	10.99	26.57	26.47	47.37	23.26	21.53	12.29	12.85	10.03
H2	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	94.19	99.63	96.20	99.73	99.06	94.58	98.89	99.56	97.65
GAM	ADT56× <i>Kalanamak</i>	21.97	54.64	53.47	57.45	47.68	55.63	25.17	26.41	20.43

DDF - Days to Fifty percent Flowering, PH - Plant Height, NPT –number of productive tillers per plant, FL – Flag leaf length, FW – Flag leaf width, PL – Panicle Length, PW – Panicle Weight, NB – Number of branches per panicle, FG – Filled Grains, UFG – Unfilled Grains, TGP –Total number of Grains per Panicle, HSW –Hundred Seed Weight, SPY – Single Plant Yield, KL – Kernel Length, KB- Kernel Breadth, LB – Length to Breadth ratio, HP-Hulling percentage; MP-milling percentage; HRR-head rice recovery; KL-kernel length; KB- kernel breadth; LBR-length-to-breadth ratio; FEB-Fe content in brown rice and FEP- Fe content in polished rice.

Fig 1. Correlation analysis among yield and nutritional traits

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